

Influence of Work-Life Balance on Employee Work Performance Among Middle Level Management Public Servants in Public Service in Kenya

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Abstract:

The aim of this study was to establish the influence of work-life balance on employee work performance among middle level management public servants in public service in Kenya. The study adopted a survey and multiple linear regression research design. Descriptive statistics provided meaningful comparisons between groups or datasets (Sudha, 2017). While multiple linear regression demonstrated the importance of the independent variables' influence on the dependent variables. It was also efficient to investigate and visualize data using descriptive statistics, as well as to develop a prediction model. Pie charts are the graphic representations that

provided visual insights into variable distribution, shape, and linkages. The study's population was the Kenya School of Government SMC 409/2012 class with 112 trainees. A purposive sampling was preferred as the SMC 409/2023 class was already in place following nomination by their respective institutions, a representation of various agencies of the Kenyan government. The class was already a controlled group in the sense that they met the minimum criteria being in mid-level management in public service and being a representation of different government agencies as well as a representation in terms of length of service in public service, age and gender. Data collection was done using a shared google link questionnaire that was sent to all participants with the intention of obtaining data from at least 74 respondents. From the results above it was clear that the respondents stated that work-life balance had a positive influence on their productivity at work. The results from the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) showed a significant statistical relationship between the overall performance at work, and work-life balance considered in the model. This is indicated by an F-value of 5.573 and a p-value of 0.002, at a 95% confidence level. The findings underscored the importance of work-life balance in enhancing employee performance in the public service. The researchers recommended that public service should adopt policies aimed at aiding employees with the attainment of work-life balance. This could mean extended working hours for reporting to work and leaving work, working from home, flex-times as well as discouraging employees from carrying work home and ensuring all employees go on leave.

Keywords: *Work-life balance, Employee work performance, middle level management, Kenyan public service, Flex-times.*

Introduction

Public service plays a crucial role in the functioning of a country. It provides essential services, maintain infrastructure, and implement policies that affect the lives of millions. The performance of employee is therefore of utmost importance. Employee performance can be significantly influenced by non-monetary motivators. Job security, a positive work environment, career development opportunities, work-life balance, job autonomy, and meaningful work are examples of motivators. Ensuring that employees have a healthy work-life balance can also help motivate them to a great extent. According to research, intrinsic motivators provide a more consistent source of enhanced engagement and productivity (Waweru, et al., 2020). Work-life balance practices are deliberate organizational changes in projects or organizational culture that are intended to lessen work-life struggle and empower workers to be more viable at work and in different tasks. The move from viewing work-life balance practices solely as a means of accommodating individual employees with care giving responsibilities to recognizing their contribution to organizational performance and employee engagement is an important paradigm shift that is still very much in progress (Maduraiveeran, 2020). Research has indicated that those workers who have some form of control over their working environment have a tendency to have less anxiety related sickness, with clear ramifications for the idea of work-life balance. The essential way organizations can encourage work-life balance for their workers is through work-life practices that are generally connected with adaptable working and decreases in working time or family. Accommodating arrangements in this manner helping in making efficient service delivery. Even if many companies have extensive work-life programs, most have not yet changed their organizational cultures to support employees and managers who want to use work-life options (Mba, 2022).

The impacts of presenting work-life balance practices on worker attitudes and perceptions incorporate employment fulfilment, proficient service delivery, work stress and turnover

objective. These components, thus, influence work execution, direct and indirect absenteeism costs, costs connected with the misfortune and substitution of esteemed workers, consumer loyalty, and organizational productivity; although the formal evaluation of work-life practices is often difficult because of the problem of calculating the costs and benefits of different strategies, some companies have attempted to quantify the outcomes of specific policies.

The existent literature suggests that work-life balance practices generally have a positive impact on individual and organizational profitability through productive service delivery. Notwithstanding, Pfizer Canada reported a 30% profitability increment in its translation office when workers were furnished with chances to work from home (Victoria O. *et al.*, 2019). This study therefore sort to contextualize the same and investigate the influence work-life balance would have on the middle level managers in the Kenyan public service.

Materials and Methods

The study adopted a survey and multiple linear regression research design. Descriptive statistics provided meaningful comparisons between groups or datasets (Sudha, 2017). While multiple linear regression demonstrated the importance of the independent variables' influence on the dependent variables. It was also efficient to investigate and visualize data using descriptive statistics, as well as to develop a prediction model. Histograms and scatter plots and pie charts are the graphic representations that provided visual insights into variable distribution, shape, and linkages. The study's population was the Kenya School of Government SMC 409/2012 class with 112 trainees. A purposive sampling was preferred as the SMC 409/2023 class was already in place following nomination by their respective institutions, a representation of various agencies of the Kenyan government. The class was already a controlled group in the sense that they met the minimum criteria being in mid-level management in public service and being a

representation of different government agencies as well as a representation in terms of length of service in public service, age and gender. To improve the accuracy and ensure all factors are captured in the model, the study used Tabachnick and Fidell to calculate the sample size for the chosen respondents since it's accurate for multiple regression analysis.

$n = 50 + 8m$ with $\alpha = 0.05$ $m =$ no. of variables $n =$ sample size

$n = 50 + 8(3)$

$n = 74$

Data collection was done using a shared google link questionnaire that was sent to all participants with the intention of obtaining data from at least 74 respondents. The response rate was satisfactory, with 76 out of 112 potential participants completing the questionnaire, exceeding the required sample size of 74.

Results

94.7%, 72 of the respondents believed that work-life balance positively affects employee performance. Two people who contributed 2.6% believed that it does not, while two people were unsure if it does or doesn't, contributing to 2.6%.

Figure 1. Influence of Work-Life Balance on Employee Performance

41 people, which is 53.2%, strongly agreed that work-life balance is extremely important for employee performance. 26%, which are 20 people, agreed that it is important for employee performance. Eight people, which is 10.4%, agreed that it moderately affects employee

performance. while 2.6%, which is two people, strongly disagreed that work-life balance affects employee performance.

Work-life balance satisfaction had a lower mean of 2.71 and a greater standard deviation of 1.030, indicating a broader range of viewpoints among respondents.

Figure 2. Importance of Work-Life Balance on Employee Performance

45.5%, Thirty-six respondents were satisfied with their current work-life balance. 11.7% of 9 respondents were very satisfied with their current work-life balance. 32.5%, 25 respondents were neutral about their work-life balance. Seven people, 9.1%, were dissatisfied with their current work-life balance, while one person, 1.3%, was very dissatisfied with the current work-life balance.

Figure 3. Satisfaction with Work-Life Balance

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to establish the influence work-life balance has on employee performance among middle level management

employees in public service in Kenya. Of the 76 senior managers who were interviewed from a population of 112 respondents, it was noted that work-life balance was an important factor in improving their performance. The results herein suggests that majority 94.7% agreed while 2.6 % disagreed with that assumption. This study therefore concurs with the study done by Victoria (2019) which suggested that profitability of Pfizer increased by 30% when employees were allowed to work from home as a result of promotion of work life balance. It also agrees with Mba (2022) whose study indicated that majority of those interviewed reported that work-life balance reduced their level of stress and anxieties thus improving their overall performance in tasks assigned at work. The mean rating for overall performance at work was 3.66 on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being terrible and 5 being extremely good, showing a fairly favorable sentiment with a standard deviation of 0.960, indicating a pretty consistent distribution of answers. Work-life balance satisfaction had a lower mean of 2.71 and a greater standard deviation of 1.030, indicating a broader range of viewpoints among respondents.

Conclusion

The study provided an in-depth analysis, presentation, and interpretation of the data collected through questionnaires. The response rate was satisfactory, with 76 out of 112 potential participants completing the questionnaire, exceeding the required sample size of 74. 94.7% of the respondents believing that work-life balance has a positive influence on work performance would then be an important guide to tier 1 management in public service especially in HR policies formulation. The data analyzed suggests that work-life balance had a significant influence on employee performance. These findings underscore the importance of this factor in enhancing employee performance in the public service. Future studies could explore other non-financial motivators and their impact on employee performance.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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